

The Implementation of Authentic Assessment to Evaluate the Students' Speaking Skill

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Abstract: The study mainly aims at describing the implementation of authentic assessment to evaluate the students' speaking skill in the classroom that conducted by lecturer. The objectives of this study were: to describe the authentic assessment implementation, lecturers' achievement, their problems, causes of their problems. The research design was case study. Two English lecturers were chosen as the subjects. The fourteen class observations, questionnaire and interview were conducted to collect the data. The data were analyzed by using Miles and Huberman' model of analysis. The findings showed that basically, two English lecturers have just implemented the authentic assessment but they have not been able to implement it completely, properly, and smoothly in speaking class yet. Some suggestions can be given in the study. They should prepare the time allotment properly before preparing, implementing, and scoring students' skill, look for many references, join workshop or conference that relating to the authentic assessment in order to understand the ways to design and implement the authentic assessment, score students' skill and practice them correctly.

Keywords: *authentic assessment, speaking*

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum change is common in education world. It should be evaluated from time to time in order to meet the needs from various parties of education. Consequently, it continually changes. One of aspects in curriculum is assessment. Assessment becomes very important issue in the learning process of higher education because it is needed by the lecturer to evaluate the development, ability and responsibility of the students. In assessment of education, a massive progress is appear. The usual assessing technique is multiple-choice test form. When multiple-choice test is considered not appropriate to

meet the objective of the learning then lecturer will try to find another alternative. One of the alternative assessments is authentic assessment. It belongs to alternative (to objective type tests) assessment which has the capacity of providing students with the opportunity to explore life-like situations by having problem solving tasks.

O'Malley and Pierce (1996) state that authentic assessment refers to the multiple forms of assessment that reflect student learning, achievement, motivation, attitudes on instructionally-relevant activities. It includes performance assessment, portfolios, and student self-assessment.

Speaking is one of four English skills in language learning. It has important role because through the speaking activity, people can communicate with the other people. Hornby (1995), states that through speaking language learners will be judged upon most in real life situation. Fauziati (2010) points out that mastering the art of speaking is the single most important aspect of learning a second or foreign language and success is measure in term of ability to carry out a conversation in the language. In oral test, the student needs accuracy and effectiveness that is the reliability and validity of an oral production test. An oral production test consists of speaking and reading skills. The students need to pay attention to pronunciation, fluency, and diction.

The authentic assessment focuses on the ideas and answers directly from the mind while non-authentic assessment focuses on test, examination and tasks. In speaking class, the lecturer is supposed to be able to implement authentic assessment to evaluate the students' speaking skills, such as oral interview, project, portfolio, experiment and etc.

In order to get the best evaluation in speaking class, English lecturers must be able to design authentic assessment, implement it, and score the students' skill by using it. Those conditions are not easy to be conducted by lecturer because those steps need much understanding and time for achieving them. The authentic assessment is comprehensive assessment in which all of the students' activities must be assessed. Some English lecturers have found problems when implementing authentic assessment.

They got difficulty to design, implement and score students' skill. That condition happened because they may not have insufficient understanding about the authentic assessment.

The study tried to describe the case of implementation of authentic assessment to evaluate the students' speaking skill that was conducted by two English lecturers of English Department of Faculty of Language and Culture UNTAG Semarang. If two English lecturers implemented authentic assessment in speaking class, how they implemented it, what achievements after implementation, what problems that were faced during implementation, and what causes of lecturer's problems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Authentic Assessment

Assessment is authentic when we directly examine students' performance on worthy intellectual tasks. O'Malley and Pierce (1996) state that authentic assessment refers to the multiple forms of assessment that reflect student learning, achievement, motivation, attitudes on instructionally-relevant activities. It includes performance assessment, portfolios, and student self-assessment. In oral interviews, students can respond orally to questions about a range of topics, and the teacher can ask probe questions to determine student comprehension or command over specific aspects of the language. In constructed-response items, students read and review textual materials and then respond to a series of open-ended questions eliciting comprehension and higher-order thinking.

2. Characteristics of Authentic Assessment

To implement authentic assessment properly, there are some crucial points that have to be understood. One of them, lecturer has to know characteristics of authentic assessment. According to Wiggins (1993), there are four parts of authentic assessment characteristics that have been discussed. They were its structures and logistics, the intellectual design features, grading and scoring standards, and fairness and equity.

3. Designing of Authentic Assessment

There are some crucial points that have to be understood to implement the authentic assessment properly. One of them, lecturer has to be able to design authentic assessment as suitable as possible to students and teaching learning process objectives. Later, designing authentic assessment requires considerable work prior to the beginning of a subject so that lecturer is suggested to be cooperated with campuses, parents, and administrations in order to gain the main purpose of the assessment. Participation of those who involve in the assessment is also important in the process for developing authentic assessment. Indeed, Baker (1993) and Herman, Aschbacher, and Winters (1992) in O'Malley and Pierce (1996: 17) give eight steps in planning and designing authentic assessment as follow: build a team, determine the purposes of the authentic assessments, specify objectives, conduct professional development on authentic assessment, collect examples of authentic assessments, adapt existing assessments or develop new ones, try out the assessments and review the assessment.

4. Types of Authentic Assessment

Three types of Authentic Assessment is performance assessment, portfolio assessment, and project assessment. Performance assessment is a kind of assessment which demands students to construct response, create a product or demonstrate application of knowledge in the form of individual or group works. In portfolio assessment, students together with lecturer can determine what topic and kind of work they will do in the form of writing and certain period of time how long they will conduct it connected to the instructional objectives. Project assessment is a kind of assessment which assesses students' task in the forms of investigation starting from the planning, data collecting, organizing, analysis, and presenting within a period of time.

5. Definition of Speaking

Fulcher (2003) states that speaking is an ability that is taken for granted, learned as it is through a process of socialization through communicating. Linse (2005) states

that speaking is equally important in young learners' language development. Cameroon (2001) states that speaking is the active use of language to express meaning so that speaking is much more demanding than listening language on learners' language resource and skills. moreover, Bailey (2000) points out that speaking is a process of interaction where speakers intend to build meaning through producing, receiving and processing information. From those theories, it can be concluded that speaking is important to communicate with other people and it is used as media to show ideas, opinions, thoughts and feeling to other.

6. Teaching Speaking

The aim of teaching and learning English in Indonesia, especially in higher education is to develop communicative skills that include the skill of listening, speaking, reading and writing proportionately. Therefore, lecturer should provide the students with speaking task and give them opportunities to use the target language to communicate with others.

According to Harmer (1998), there are three basic reasons why it is a good idea to give students speaking task with provoke them to use all and any language at their comments. Those are:

a) Rehearsal

Getting student to have a free discussions, gives them a chance to rehearse having discussions outside the classroom. Lecturer asks students to rehearse outside classroom in order to know how their speaking ability can improve. From those, students can improve their speaking ability except in the class.

b) Feedback

Speaking tasks where students are trying to use all and any language that they know to provide feedback for both lecturer and students. Lecturer can see how well their class is doing and what language problems they have. Students can also see how easy they find

a particular kind of speaking and what they need to do to improve. Students activities can give them enormous confidence and satisfaction, and with sensitive lecturer guidance a can encourage them into further study.

c) Engagement

Good speaking activities can be highly motivating. If all students are participating fully and if lecturer has set up the activity properly and can give sympathetic and useful feedback, they will get tremendous satisfaction from it. Many speaking tasks (role-play, discussion, problem solving etc) are intrinsically enjoyable in themselves.

d) Assessment of Speaking Skill

To know the improvement of students' speaking skills has been made by the students after being treated by some problem sticks, their speaking ability will be assessed by speaking measurement adapted from Arthur Hughes collaborated with FSI (foreign service instate). There are five components have rating range from 1-6 with different weighting point from the lowest to the highest. The speaking measurement contains of some component elaborated from students' skill including their pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency and comprehension.

METHODOLOGY

Design of the study used Case Study. Two English lecturers were chosen as the subject. Fourteen Observations, some interviews and some questionnaires were conducted to collect the data. The data were analyzed by using Miles and Huberman' model of analysis (Flow Model). It is an on-going activity throughout the whole investigation. It is chosen because in this model, the data can be analyzed interactively and continuously until the data are saturated. The procedure of data analysis can be drawn as below:

4. Causes of English Lecturers' Problems

From the data, that can be found that the causes of English Lecturers' problems were insufficient allotment time, lack of understanding in designing authentic assessment, implementing it and scoring students' skill. Two English lecturers were not able to implement the authentic assessment to evaluate students' speaking skill completely yet.

Basically, Two English lecturers have implemented the authentic assessment but they have not been able to implement the authentic assessment properly and smoothly yet. They also have not been able to manage the time allotment, determine the characteristics of authentic assessment, define its purposes, design its steps, implement it and score the students' skill. Some problems were found in managing the time allotment, preparing or designing the authentic assessment, implementing the authentic assessment, and scoring students' skills. Some causes of problems have been found in the study. They were insufficient allotment time that caused lecturers were not able to manage the time in the classroom properly, lack of understanding in designing authentic assessment that caused lecturers got difficulty to design authentic assessment, Lack of understanding in implementing authentic assessment that caused lecturers were not able to implement it in a small and big classes and implement it to heterogeneous students properly yet, and lack of understanding in scoring students' skill that caused lecturers were not able to score many aspects in authentic assessment and implement self and peer-assessment yet because of its subjectivity among students.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings and discussion, two English lecturers were not able to design and implement authentic assessment to evaluate students' speaking skill completely yet. They should prepare the time allotment properly before designing authentic assessment, implementing authentic assessment, and scoring students' speaking skill. Second, They should look for many references from many sources or join workshop or conference that relating to authentic assessment implementation in

order to they can understand the ways to prepare or design and implement the authentic assessment, score students' skill and practice them in the classroom correctly and smoothly.

From this result of the study, suggestions can be given for lecturer how to plan and focus on units of meaningful learning, use varieties of meaningful learning and engaging assessment opportunities, provide students with a rubric of agreed-upon criteria relating to the course outcomes before undertaking assessment tasks, test student-constructed rubrics on a sample of student work initially to improve validity and reliability. It also can add lecture's knowledge on how to assess the student's speaking skill and a pragmatic aspect which is need added in rubric score. Therefore, for other researchers who consider conducting such authentic assessment in assessing speaking in order to be better and perfect. For the readers, can understand more about authentic assessment especially in implementing the student's speaking in teaching learning process.

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